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Professional Standard of a Teacher in Extended Education: Goals and Implementation Issues

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Abstract

In the modern world, scientific and technological progress, the development of production and technology, as well as the changing labor market require the constant development of the professional skills and competences of an employee. Qualification directories, in turn, gradually become obsolete: neither they do not have any new professions at all nor their description does not correspond to reality. This is why it is needed to change the current system of qualifications by changing the system of professional standards. The need to develop and introduce professional standards was determined by Presidential Decree No. 597 of May 7, 2012 "On Measures to Implement State Social Policy." In accordance with this order, the professional standard is defined as a characteristic of a qualification necessary for the employee to perform a certain type of professional activity and is applied by:

- employers when forming HR policy and management, in the organization of training and certification of employees, the development of job descriptions, work rates, the confement of tariff categories to employees and the establishment of wage systems, taking into account the specifics of work organization, labor and management;
- educational organizations of professional education when developing professional educational programs;
- in terms of developing federal state educational standards for vocational education according to established procedure.

The implementation of a professional standard also affects the system of extended education. (Order of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Russian Federation of September 8, 2015 No. 613N "On the Approval of the Professional Standard" Teacher of Extended Education for Children and Adults, "an order of the Deputy Minister of Education and Science of the Russian Federation V. Kaganov of April 29, 2016). The paper presents the results of a survey of teachers working in extended education in Kazan. The research objective is to study the teachers` opinion about implementing professional standard in their work, career growth and professional development with the help of our special questionnaire.

Keywords: professional standard, extended education, teacher education, system of education.

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Introduction

Such realities of the modern world as scientific and technological progress, manufacturing and technological advances, together with constant changes in the labor market, demand that employees continuously improve their professional skills and expertise. For this reason, a system of Professional standards actively evolves. Professional standard is a document that gives holistic up-to-date information about the requirements employees must satisfy in order to perform their duties properly (Buylova, 2005). Professional standards help to manage human resources effectively and manage employees (The procedure for attestation of teaching staff., 2014). The document is used to review teachers' performance, determine the salary, issue job descriptions, and execute employment agreements.

Problem statement

A Professional standard of extended education teachers was introduced on January 1st, 2017, and is now mandatory.

The Professional standard stipulates that an educator must do the following:

- Carry out admission of children in accordance with an established program.
- Select children in accordance with an established program (together with a committee).
- Motivate pupils.
- Design measures aimed at supplying the classroom with physical materials.
- Prepare necessary informational materials.
- Consult pupils and their parents.
- Help and control the pupils.
- Improve children's behavior.
- Understand pupils' needs.
- Divide pupils into groups while taking into consideration characteristics of educational programs.
- Ensure preservation and the correct use of physical materials, equipment, etc.
- Create an environment that will stimulate children's development.
- Prepare students for participation in contests, expositions, and similar events.
- Create conditions that will improve children's self-esteem and self-control.
- Cooperate with colleagues and create a proper working atmosphere (Gulchevskaya et.al, 2011).

Let me outline the main points of the Professional standard of extended education teachers.

The Professional standard is a complex of generalized job functions by performing which a general goal will be achieved. Each of the generalized functions incorporates a complex of job functions, where as a job function is divided into job actions, skills, and knowledge necessary to fulfill that function.

Let us see what generalized job functions are.

1. Teaching in programs of extended education for children and adults;

2. Organizational and methodical support of the teaching process in programs of extended education for children and adults;

3. Organizational and pedagogic support necessary to implement programs of extended education for children and adults;

1. Teaching in programs of extended education for children and adults includes the following functions:

- Organization of the pupils' activity in such a way that will allow them to master programs of extended education;

- Organization of extracurricular activities for the pupils who receive extended education;

- Communicating with the parents (legal representatives) of the pupils who receive extended education in order to facilitate teaching and education.

- Pedagogic control and evaluation of how the pupils master extended education programs;

2. Organizational and methodical support necessary to implement programs of extended education:

- Organization and execution of supply-and-demand research in the sector of extended education for children and adults;

- Organizational and pedagogic support of methodical activities of extended education teachers;

- Tracking and evaluation of how the teachers implement extended education programs;

3. Organizational and pedagogic support necessary to implement programs of extended education:

- Organization and execution of mass extracurricular events;

- Organizational and pedagogic support of social partnership development and promotion of extended education programs for children and adults.

- Organization of extended education for children and adults in one or several directions (Malykhina, 2009).

Results and Discussions

Reasoning from the general description of the activity, the Professional standard allows educators to “stack” functions of a separate employee. All the outlined functions must not be performed by one multiskilled staff worker. They are to be distributed between all employees involved in the process. Distributing and management, together with tracking how these functions are performed, are carried out by the head of a given extended education institution (Loginova, 2008).

Implementation of the Professional standard in the sphere of extended education raises a very important question: “will the introduction of the Professional standard improve education quality and lead to teachers' professional growth?”

In the light of that question, a survey among extended education teachers was conducted. It was aimed at determining teachers' opinion about the place the Professional standard has in their work, career advancement and professional growth. A special questionnaire was designed in order to conduct the survey.

258 extended education teachers participated in the research; among them 35 are men and 193 are women. The age of the participants is between 24 and 54. The teaching service record varies from 3 to 35 years.

60.4% (156 people) of the survey participants think that Professional standards are useful for the evaluation of teachers' work; 26.8% of the participants (69 people) hold that Professional standards are not

always useful for the evaluation of teachers' work; 12.8% (33 people) of the teachers say that Professional standards must not be used for the evaluation of teachers' work.

87.2% (225 people) of the participants note that Professional standards play an important role in their professional growth; 12.8% (33 people) of the teachers do not think that Professional standards are important for their professional growth. At the same time, 100% of the participants point out that they often discussed Professional standards with their colleagues.

61.6% (159 people) of the participants think that Professional standards are a useful tool aimed at the improvement of education. At the same time, 67.8% of the respondents note that Professional standards clearly define what is expected from teachers.

73.3% (189 people) of the participants point out that Professional standards are useful for the formulation of teachers' key tasks, which, in turn, can improve their proficiency.

33.3% (86 people) hold that Professional standards can be effectively used to facilitate the professional growth of teachers.

100% of the teachers say that they must be consulted with during the development of Professional standards.

79.5% of the participants (205 people) stress that Professional standards are important for the improvement of teachers' expertise.

81.4% (210 people) of the participants note that Professional standards help to improve the Professional status of teachers. 76.7% of the teachers (198 people) say that Professional standards help to bring the profession of teaching closer to perfection.

At the same time, teachers point out that Professional standards impose bureaucratic control on educators (59.7% of the participants) and that Professional standards are a means to increase the degree of teacher's accountability (34.5% of the participants).

60.9% (157 people) of the participants emphasize that Professional standards are the basis for the selection of entrants who are aspiring to become teachers.

55.8% (144 people) of the teachers state that Professional standards play a key role when the decision regarding promotions is being made.

46.1% (119 people) of the teachers note that Professional standards play an important role in the certification of educators.

82.2% (212 people) of the participants say that Professional standards play a significant role in the identification of good teachers.

44.6% (115 people) of the teachers stress that Professional standards provide the basis on which the minimal proficiency of teachers is compared.

61.6% (159 people) of the teachers hold that Professional standards are an essential element in the improvement of education quality and teachers' professional growth. 76.7% (198 people) of the teachers point out that Professional standards are important for determining what teachers must be able to do.

71.7% (185 people) of the participants emphasize that the presence of Professional standards is useful while conducting discussions with the public; 96.9% (150 people) of the survey participants say that Professional standards are a basis for the evaluation of their teaching practice; 65.1% (168 people) of the teachers point out that it is important to use professional standards to develop professional dialog; 72.8 % (187 people) of the teachers stress that Professional standards facilitate the constructive debate over teachers' proficiency.

Answering the question “In your opinion, in what direction should the Professional standards in the sphere of education develop? Why?” 30.2% (78 people) of the teachers say that Professional standards should be designed by teachers; 22.9% (59 people) of the survey participants stress that more attention must be paid to practice rather than theory; 11.2% (29 people) of the teachers say that there must be less unnecessary paperwork; 22.5% (58 people) of the teachers state that there must be more communication with the children and that various games and class forms must be employed; 13.2% (34 people) of the teachers say that training and workshops are required in order to develop Professional standards.

Among important parameters of their work, the teachers highlight the following:

Cooperation with colleagues – 17.4% of the teachers

Working on pupils’ behavior – 20.9% of the teachers

Class planning – 17.4% of the teachers

Evaluation of the pupils’ work – 4.7% of the teachers

Reflection on my own work during classes – 34.5% of the teachers

Talking to the pupils’ parents – 22.9% of the teachers

Working at my professional training – 14% of the teachers

Joint use of materials with my colleagues – 14.3% of the teachers

Supporting the education of the pupils – 38% of the teachers

Creation of new materials to facilitate the pupils’ education – 48.4% of the teachers

Motivational work with the pupils’ – 25.2% of the teachers

Designing new strategies that will improve the quality of pupils’ education – 38% of the teachers

Among the most important factors of professional training and career growth of the last five years, teachers name participation in grant projects – 5.8% of the respondents; participation and winning different contests of professional skills – 22.9% of the respondents; advanced training courses – 34.5% of the teachers; the pupils’ participation or winning different contests – 38% of the teachers; participation in workshops – 19% of the respondents; participation in research and practice conferences of different levels – 37.6% of the teachers.

Answering the question “How do you use Professional standards while planning your professional training?” 34.5% of the participants say they use the standards while planning classes; 30.6% of the participants use the standards while planning the technological component; 30.6% of the teachers use the standards for their off-class activity; 37.2% of the teachers use the standards while developing course programs; 38.8% of the teachers use the standards for self-education and while preparing for classes.

Answering the question “What relationship must exist between Professional standards and evaluation of teachers?” 40.7% of the survey participants say that the professional standards increase the responsibility for the results, qualification, and criteria of the evaluation; 38% of the participants state that they must be in agreement; 26.7% of the teachers say that there should be an individual approach to each particular case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, speaking of teachers’ general attitude towards Professional standards, the following can be said: 61.6% (159 people) of the teachers generally approve of Professional standards and their evaluation; 26.4% (68 people) of the teachers regard Professional standards differently, and it can be said

that these teachers take the middle position regarding the use of the standards in their work (it all depends on particular circumstances); 12% (31 people) of the teachers have a negative attitude to Professional standards.

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